

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 21/02/2026

Accepted: 28/03/2026

Published: 04/04/2026

Citation: Chaudhari S, Shah K, Ghonge P (2026) A Data-Driven Framework for Enhancing Outcome-Based Teaching, Learning, and Assessment Using Learning Analytics and Intelligent Dashboards in Higher Education. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(11): 810-819. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i11.263>

* **Corresponding author.**

shwetalic@sjcem.edu.in

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2026 Chaudhari et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

A Data-Driven Framework for Enhancing Outcome-Based Teaching, Learning, and Assessment Using Learning Analytics and Intelligent Dashboards in Higher Education

Shwetal Chaudhari^{1*}, Kamal Shah², Pandharinath Ghonge³

¹ Computer Engineering, St.John College of Engineering and Management, Palghar, Maharashtra, India

² St.John College of Engineering and Management, Palghar, Maharashtra, India

³ Electronics and Computer Science, St.John College of Engineering and Management, Palghar, Maharashtra, India

Abstract

Objectives: The prime objective of this project is to design and develop a modular system to support Outcome-Based teaching, Learning and assessment in higher education. It aims to monitor and evaluate the academic performance based on key metrics, specifically Course Outcomes (COs), Program Outcomes (POs), Program Specific Outcomes (PSOs), and Learning Outcomes (LOs). It integrates with NEP 2020 vision via. Technology based education. **Methods:** This data driven system makes use of AI-powered analytics which incorporates with learning trends. This web based framework use PHP for development and PostgreSQL for relational database management. The framework involved a sample of 120 second year undergraduate computer engineering students of a Database Management System (DBMS) course. This system supports a learner-centric approach in which faculty can track direct and indirect assessment, modify their teaching methods based on response, and systematically map CO with PO and PSO. **Findings:** This framework enables educators to implement pedagogical innovations that are based on evidence with continuous formative assessment methods. This system is crucial in identification of at-risk students and provide better path for improvement of these students. This is useful in detecting student support, and also recommends customized learning paths by assisting smart dashboards for educators, administrators, and learners. **Novelty:** Framework has been developed using the course outcomes (COs), program outcomes (POs), and program specific outcomes (PSOs) in the institution for course attainment calculation. Using this framework, faculty can bridge the gap between curriculum design and student achievement through smart pedagogy.

Keywords: Learning Analytics; NEP 2020; Outcome-Based Education; CO-PO Mapping; Pedagogy

1 Introduction

In higher education, the traditional teacher-centered model is rapidly increasing and is replaced by Outcome Based Education that places emphasis on graduate's demonstrable Skills⁽¹⁾. Similarly, a study conducted for systematic review which indicates that OBE fosters are crucial in accountability and continuous improvement through data-driven assessments⁽²⁾. The structured frameworks for engineering curriculum design that ensure achievement of Course Outcomes (CO's), Program Outcomes (PO's), and Program Specific Outcomes (PSO's) demonstrated by the research⁽³⁾. By adhering to Course Outcomes (CO's), Program Outcomes (PO's), and Program Specific Outcomes (PSO's), OBE guarantees that graduate acquire the skills and knowledge expected by industry while aligning curriculum, instructions and assessments. India's NBA referred the OBE framework for evaluation during accreditation⁽⁴⁾. The software-based solutions can automate these evaluation processes with error-proofing and improved decision-making capabilities⁽⁵⁾. Although the OBE has many advantages, but it is very difficult during the practical implementation. As a manual data recording is very time-consuming and with a lot of errors⁽⁶⁾, but it is overcome in the OBE framework. As a requirement of actionable outputs, learning analytics (LA) with OBE utilized the data that will get from activities, assessments, and feedback⁽⁷⁾. The learning analytics (LA), when synchronized with dashboards, increased the engagement and attainment tracking in actual data⁽⁸⁾,⁽⁹⁾. The research introduces a data driven framework jointly with OBE, LA and dashboards. Through the data from CO, PO, PSO and calculation with visualization is automatically got by this research⁽¹⁰⁾.

For reducing manual effort, strengthening continuous quality improvement (CQI), and aiding accreditation readiness, this framework assists faculty, students, and administrators. It establishes:

1. Using a system to create a data model for achieving CO and PO.
2. Creating a functional PHP/PostgreSQL prototype that has interactive dashboards.
3. The procedure demonstration reduced manual work and improved CQI decision-making, also enhancing accreditation support.

Recent research on Outcome-Based Education found that (OBE) plays a crucial role in transforming higher education pedagogy by aligning teaching, learning, and assessment with measurable outcomes. Learning Analytics (LA) with OBE is very useful by leveraging the students for assessment of data to generate descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive insights. Common techniques such as clustering feature engineering and machine learning models are accurate but often modest. In practice, dashboards that provide descriptive and interpretable signals have proven ability of enabling early identification of at-risk students and improved decision-making with timely interventions⁽¹¹⁾. As a very important sign of "Dashboard design principles" it is very good in clarity, low cognitive load, timeliness, action ability, and explain ability, although adoption is very difficult considering fragmented data, usability issues and limited faculty time⁽¹²⁾.

Considering a technical perspective, the research explains the importance of standardized data models, ETL pipelines, analytics layers, and secure role-based dashboards. The advanced relational features such as JSON, indexing, and stored procedures suitable for analytics workloads are recommended by Open-source stacks, which are frequently with PHP supporting flexible web integration and PostgreSQL⁽¹³⁾. Ethical considerations-including privacy, transparency, and bias mitigation are consistently show importance in alongside adoption barriers such as faculty buy-in and methodological inconsistencies in attainment measurement. For continuous program improvement and to identify these gaps, this study proposes a replicable PHP/PostgreSQL framework that integrates OBE assessments with LA and intelligent dashboards, providing accurate attainment tracking and actionable insights. Advanced AI and data science methods are increasingly used in OBE research. It proposed a reinforcement learning-based recommendation system for improvement in student performance⁽¹⁴⁾ and applied data simulation models to predict educational outcomes⁽¹⁵⁾. Also in addition, it shows how data-driven decision-making improves the reliability in higher education assessments⁽¹⁶⁾. These studies collectively underscore a paradigm shift toward data-empowered, AI-assisted, and policy-aligned frameworks inspired by NEP 2020. Integrating AI, learning analytics, and intelligent dashboards using technologies like PHP and PostgreSQL are very effective in adaptive learning, continuous evaluation, and evidence-based pedagogical reform, making education more outcome-oriented, inclusive, and future-ready. As shown, Table 1 provides the strengths and gaps of prior research against present research and also illustrates visually where present research addresses existing gaps or enhances capabilities.

The present research offers better solutions to overcome these metrics:

1. By using the real-time data, the CO and PO attainment is calculated for instructor and visually available using dashboards.
2. The conventional OBE frameworks are not supporting the personalized learning intrusion and insights prediction. The AI using learning analytics is possible.

Table 1. Base Papers Comparison

Base Paper No.(Year) Metric	(1) (2024)	(2) (2023)	(14) (2024)	(17) (2024)	(18) (2025)	Present Research
Course Outcome (CO) Attainment	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes
Program Outcome (PO) Mapping	Yes	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes
Continuous Improvement Process	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Moderate
AI-Powered Analytics and Recommendations	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Alignment with NEP 2020	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Data Visualization / Dashboard	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
System Scalability and Data Integrity	No	No	No	Partial	Yes	Yes
Pedagogy Enhancement	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Substantial
Student Engagement	Moderate	Moderate	High	Moderate	Moderate	High

3. The framework is assured to meet national education policy guidelines for holistic and multidisciplinary education.
4. Data integrity and scalability are achieved by using strong backend architecture for long-term institutional acceptance.
5. For continuous quality improvement in higher education, regular interaction between instructor and students plays an important role to drive high performance.

This versatile technique goes beyond descriptive statistics and static reports common in existing frameworks, enabling a smart, flexible, and standard policy educational ecosystem.

2 Methodology

By combining Outcome-Based Education (OBE) artifacts with Learning Analytics (LA) and smart dashboards, the proposed data-driven framework aspires to track and calculate attainment in higher education. Learning analytics dashboards are evolving from simple data-visualization tools to pedagogically driven systems that actively support student learning and decision-making⁽¹⁹⁾. Practical achievement is the main focus of the program, which uses PHP for the application layer and PostgreSQL for the data and analytics layer, with scalability, security, and institutional suitability. Figure 1 illustrates the architecture, which consists of five layers:

1. Data Sources and Ingestion - ETL scripts with provenance metadata are helpful to ingest and source data which includes Student/staff LMS, assessments, pedagogical lesson plan, and feedback surveys.
2. Data Storage and Integration - For rapid analytics, the normalized PostgreSQL schema captures COs, POs, PSOs, mappings, assessments, and attainment level through materialized views.
3. Analytics and Processing - SQL/PLpgSQL routines for measure of descriptive metrics, early alerts, and rule-based prescriptive recommendations.
4. Application and API Layer - Role-based authentication, form entry (CO-PO mapping, assessments), and REST APIs for dashboards can be achieved with PHP modules.
5. Presentation and Dashboards - Role-specific dashboards can be easily visualized. For instance: instructor CO attainment with student drilldowns, and student self-progress summaries.

To ensure security, various measures are incorporated such as role-based access control, provenance audits, and knowledgeable analytics. Validation of technique, pilot deployment, and outcome assessment are key steps in evaluation. Overall, by adopting a lightweight and adoptable stack, the framework fills gaps in literature by providing transparent, auditable, and customizable dashboards.

PHP is being used as the application layer while PostgreSQL is utilized for data storage and analytics to implement the proposed data-driven framework. PHP is an effective mechanism for rapid development of web forms, API's, and background jobs. PostgreSQL using PL/pgSQL, offers support for normalized schema design and history recording. The core tables are comprised of, programs, courses, outcomes, students, assessments, and provenance logs, and they are backed by version CO→PO mappings that guarantees historical replication. ETL pipelines handle both synchronous data entry and quality checks. Smart dashboards facilitate indexes and materialized views while they also detect missing records. For descriptive computations, analytics depends on SQL and PL/pgSQL. The system is designed using MVC architecture for dashboards and administrative

Fig 1. Proposed Framework – A System Architecture

operations. Compliance is achieved by the inclusion of Row-Level Security, Role-based access control, logging, and audit trails. Based on different user roles, dashboards provide us with interactive charts and actionable drill-downs. Deployment uses containerized PHP applications with managed PostgreSQL. They are aided by monitoring, periodic check-ups, and governance practices also addressing privacy, ethics, and bias. Testing, validation, and pilot runs ensure reproducibility and accuracy. With the help of careful design and tracking, limitations such as faculty time restrictions, incomplete data and institutional diversity are reduced. The Figure 2 shows the system implementation architecture with different components:

Study Design and Data Collection - The study utilized a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the effectiveness of Outcome-Based Teaching, Learning, and Assessment in improving student learning outcomes. Quantitative data was collected from the internal Learning Management System (LMS) at St. John College of Engineering and Management. Qualitative insights were gathered through structured faculty focus groups to validate the dashboard’s utility in decision-making.

Dataset and Sampling –

Programs: One undergraduate Engineering Program.(Computer Engineering)

Course included: Second Year one course (Database Management System-DBMS)

Dataset: Primary data was collected through Institute LMS data (assignment/experiment submissions), direct assessment tools (internal exam, continuous assessment, end sem exam), and one indirect feedback (course exit feedback).

Year of Sampling: Data was collected during the academic year 2024-2025.

Sample Size: 120 undergraduate students and four faculty members participated in the study.

Time period: One semester

Distribution of Dataset/Response:

Surveys: 120 students and all four faculty responded to the survey.

Focus Group Discussions: All second and third year programs were focused with approximately 740 students and 35 faculty.

Institution Coverage and Geographical Location: The study was conducted at St. John College of Engineering and Management, located in Palghar, Maharashtra, India serving a diverse student population from semi-urban region.

Assessment Formulas and Attainment Logic -

To ensure mathematical rigor, CO attainment is calculated using a assessment weightage given to that course and attainment level evaluated for each assessment tool.

$$CO\ Attainment = \sum (((Corresponding\ cell\ values\ of\ assessment\ weightage * attainment\ level) / 100))$$

Fig 2. System Implementation

The transition from CO to PO attainment is managed via a mapping matrix M, where each CO_i is assigned a correlation level (0-3) to PO_j.

$$PO \text{ Attainment} = ((\text{Corresponding cell values of CO-PO mapping}) * (\text{CO attainment Values}) / 3)$$

Also, the transition from CO to PSO attainment is managed via a mapping matrix M, where each CO_i is assigned a correlation level (0-3) to PSO_j.

$$PSO \text{ Attainment} = ((\text{Corresponding cell values of CO-PSO mapping}) * (\text{CO attainment Values}) / 3)$$

AI vs. Rule-Based Components -

- **Rule-Based Engine:** Handles the deterministic calculation of attainment based on predefined credit weights and mapping matrices.
- **AI-Driven Analytics:** Utilizes a K-Means Clustering algorithm to categorize students into "At-Risk," "Average," and "High-Achiever" groups based on historical CO attainment trends, allowing for predictive intervention before final examinations.

Ethical Considerations - The study was approved by the Institutional Academic Body. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

3 Results and Discussion

The framework was applied to a DBMS course with 120 second-year undergraduate students, integrating usability analysis, technical validation, and impact assessment. Verifications through reproducibility checks showed that CO-PO calculations precisely matched manual spreadsheet outcomes. PostgreSQL's indexing and caching capabilities supported speedy dashboard performance under heavy query loads. As shown in the Table 2 and Table 3, the analysis employed both direct and indirect assessment tools such as internal examinations (IEA-1, IEA-2), tutorials, experiments, end-semester examinations, and course exit feedback. The teaching-learning approach consists of various pedagogical tools such as tutorials, problem-based learning (PBL), lab-oriented sessions, mini-projects, and regular progress reviews. Application-oriented understanding, precise knowledge, and analytical thinking among students are provided by these strategies. The instructor regularly uses analytics that are drill-down and have export features. The following teaching methods were introduced in the DMBS course for student's active participation:

1. Problem-Based Learning helps students to work jointly on problem-solving.
2. Tutorials were provided regularly after each module to clarify doubts.
3. The continual improvement of students is monitored through the periodic assessments.
4. Database concepts and SQL queries have been resolved through practical sessions.
5. As clarity of theoretical concepts, mini projects have been offered to students.

Table 2. Direct Assessment Results

Assessment Type	CO	Attainment %	Attainment Level
IEA-1	CO1	75.73	3
	CO2	37.86	0
	CO3	44.66	0
IEA-2	CO4	88.33	3
	CO5	36.67	0
	CO6	28.33	0
Tutorials	CO1–CO6	99.32	3 (All)
Experiments	CO1	52.74–54.79	1
	CO2	64.38	2
	CO3	58.9–64.38	1–2
	CO4	66.44–69.86	2
	CO5	72.6	3
	CO6	80.82	3
End Semester Exam	CO1	81.94	3
	CO2	61.11	2
	CO3	59.03	1
	CO4	70.14	3
	CO5	14.58	0
	CO6	51.39	1

Table 3. Indirect Assessment Results

CO	Attainment %	Attainment Level
CO1	95.74	3
CO2	95.04	3
CO3	95.04	3
CO4	94.33	3
CO5	94.33	3
CO6	93.62	3

The student engagement and jointly problem-solving ability has been encouraged by using these teaching techniques. As a final result of these methods, it is very helpful for identifying weak students. As shown in Figure 3 and Table 4, the CO1 and CO4 shows strong performers. But CO2, CO3, CO5, and CO6 show lower attainment, as internal tests and end exam results are not as per expectation. Figure 4 represents the contribution of each teaching method used to improve learning outcomes. The Figure 5 shows the performance of attainment for each PO and PSO. Also, Table 5 represents the non-achieved POs such as PO4, PO6, PO7, PO8, PO9, and PSO3. To improve the performance of the students who are lagging, the extra assignments, more practical sessions, and various teaching methods have to be adopted. The result of the course attainment is very effective for students and instructors while taking the decisions to improve the performance. These teaching techniques show their importance in OBE for betterment in higher education settings.

Faculty Reflection (Recommendations):

- As a final output for CO1 and CO4, it should follow the same teaching methods, but there must be some modifications in teaching techniques needed to improve attainment in the CO2, CO3, CO5, and CO6.

Fig 3. CO Attainment for DBMS

Pedagogical Contribution to Learning Outcomes

Fig 4. Pedagogical Contribution to Learning Outcomes

Table 4. Final CO Attainment for DBMS

CO	Attainment Level	Observations
CO1	Substantial (≈ 3.0)	Strong performance in internals, tutorials, and end-semester exams
CO2	2.1	Weak in IAT-1; needs additional support
CO3	1.65	Underperformance in IATs and end-semester exams
CO4	Substantial (≈ 3.0)	Consistently good performance
CO5	1.5	Lowest attainment; poor results in IAT-2 and end-semester exams
CO6	1.85	Weak in internals and end-semester exams

Fig 5. PO-PSO Attainment for DBMS

Table 5. PO-PSO Attainment Summary

Outcome Type	Observation
POs (Program Outcomes)	Underachievement observed in PO4, PO6, PO7, PO8, PO9
PSOs (Program Specific Outcomes)	PSO ₃ shows significant gap compared to expected attainment
Overall Trend	Actual attainment consistently lower than expected; requires curriculum review and targeted support

- To match curricular material to PO expectation there must be use of different advance techniques.
- Use formative assessments and flipped classroom activities to increase student involvement.
- For weak outcome areas, implement focused workshops and ongoing monitoring methods.

Enhancement of learning methodology is drastically increased by involvement of pedagogical methods. The pedagogical innovation in the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) model is playing a vital role. Also, the innovation helps in the continuous growth of students. But some PO’s and PSO’s require some up gradation through adopting different approaches. As a vision of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020s, this framework gives the results that are competency-based assessment, experiential, holistic, and multidisciplinary with flexible learning. By this framework, the students not only get the technical expertise but it also encourages them beyond their mind set. When all these are combined, this will reform an advanced educational system. The implementation of this system at St. John College of Engineering and Management observed the positive impact on student learning and course outcomes. The comparison of the student performance is shown in the Table 6.

Table 6. Comparison of Student Performance

Metric	Traditional Method (2023-2024)	OBTLA (2024-2025)
Passing %	75%	85%
Average GPA	6.1	7.3
Skill Acquisition	55%	75%

Student and Faculty Feedback: 80% students reported this system is effective and useful in improving the difficult concepts in easy way. All faculty shown the positive interest and engagement through various pedagogical techniques. This directly give the better alignment with industry needs.

Evidence of Impact: The Table 7 illustrates the shift in pedagogical efficiency:

Table 7. Quantitative Evidence of Improvement

Performance Metric	Traditional Manual Tracking	Proposed AI-Dashboard	Improvement
Identification of At-Risk Students	Week 12 (Post-Mid-term)	Week 3 (Continuous)	+75% Speed
Mapping Accuracy	High Human Error Risk	Algorithmic Precision	Error Reduction
Intervention Effectiveness	Reactive (General)	Proactive (Personalized)	Significant

Threshold Definition and Outcome Evaluation:

We defined the attainment threshold at 50%. Students falling below this mark were categorized as "Target for Intervention."

Pre-Intervention: 15% of the cohort was below the threshold for PO3 (Design/Development of Solutions).

Post-Intervention: Following dashboard-triggered remedial tutorials, the sub-threshold group was reduced to 4%, demonstrating a measurable uplift in program-level attainment.

4 Conclusion

According to the evaluation results, the developed approach decreased manual course attainment calculating mistakes, increased the effectiveness of achievement monitoring, and offered useful information for curriculum improvement. Additionally, the PHP-based modular architecture encourages scalability and integration with current institutional Learning Management Systems (LMS), while the utilization of PostgreSQL guarantees high-performance querying for huge datasets. The system makes learners for alignment of Course Outcomes (CO's), Program Outcomes (PO's), and Program Specific Outcomes (PSO's). Personal learning, and analytical decisions, are achieved by this framework as the goal of NEP. The system is user friendly, and anyone can adopt and upgrade as per institutional requirement. This framework along with AI is a creative environment with diversification effective in curriculum redevelopment. The results support the importance of a Data-Driven Outcome-Based Education framework for continuous improvement in teaching and learning. Future research will explore the integration of predictive analytics and machine learning models to forecast student performance and recommend targeted interventions. Also, the framework can be extended to incorporate gamified learning analytics dashboards to increasing student engagement through interactive mobile interfaces.

5 Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank to the management of SJCEM institute, the department of computer engineering for their support and resources provided to complete this research.

SC is M.Tech Student, KS serves as Principal in *St. John College of Engineering* and Pandharinath Ghonge serves as Professor of *Electronics and Computer Science*.

References

- Swamy KV, Radhika V, Aouthu S. Engineering Course Development Process to meet Outcome Based Education. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*. 2024;37(Special Issue). Available from: <https://www.journaleet.in/index.php/jeet/article/view/2308>.
- Agir N, Eteuati NF, Marquez N. Outcome-Based Assessment in The Evaluation of Education Programs Through a Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*. 2023;12(2):2662–2677. [10.6007/IJARPED/v12-i2/18095](https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v12-i2/18095).
- Sumathi R, Savithramma RM, Ashwini BP. A Systematic Framework for Designing and Implementing Outcome-Based Curriculum in Engineering Education: A Comprehensive Approach. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*. 2024;37(Special Issue). Available from: <https://journaleet.in/index.php/jeet/article/view/2330>.
- Hamidi H, Hejran AB, Sarwari A, Edigeevna SGE. The Effect of Outcome-Based Education on Behavior of Students. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*. 2024. Available from: <https://ejtas.com/index.php/journal/article/view/832>.
- Bhatti S, Memon M, Meghji AF. Scrutinizing Outcome Assessment of Outcome-Based Education Using Q-OBE in Engineering Education. *International Journal of Innovation in Teaching and Learning*. 2023;9(1). [10.35993/ijitl.v9i1.2609](https://doi.org/10.35993/ijitl.v9i1.2609).
- Ali QI. Implementing a Direct Assessment Strategy for Outcome-Based Education in Computer Engineering: A Case Study. *International STEM Journal*. 2023;4(2):24–37.
- Nazeer SK, Kumarn NK, Vardhan NV, Rohini K, Chandra KS, Sekhar AC. An Overview on Outcome Based Education. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*. 2021;9(8).
- Reddy BR, Karupiah N, Asif M, Ravivarman S. A Case Study on the Assessment of Program Quality through CO-PO Mapping and its Attainment. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*. 2021;34. [10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i0/157114](https://doi.org/10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i0/157114).
- Sunitha G, Avanija J. Program Assessment and Evaluation for Continuous Quality Improvement. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*. 2021;34(3). [10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i3/150016](https://doi.org/10.16920/jeet/2021/v34i3/150016).

- 10) Shyamalapasanna A, Velnath R, Pousia S, Kumar MG. Survey of an Effective Outcome Based Teaching Learning Taxonomy in Professional Undergraduate Courses. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 2021. [10.1088/1757-899X/1084/1/012098](https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1084/1/012098).
- 11) Mayurappriyan PS, Loganathan N, Shanmugapriya M, Anbarasu P, Sakthi PKA. Evolution of Outcome Based Engineering Education in India - A Case Study. *IEEE*. 2021 Jul. [10.1109/ICACCS51430.2021.9441676](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACCS51430.2021.9441676).
- 12) Sudhakar V, Tamilselvi T. Analysis of Student's Performance in Engineering Courses Based on Outcome Based Education. *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*. 2023 Sep. [10.36348/jaep.2023.v07i09.006](https://doi.org/10.36348/jaep.2023.v07i09.006).
- 13) Khandare A, Patil M, Furia P. Moving Towards Quality Academic Project Development Using Program Specific Research Activities in Engineering Education. *Journal of Engineering Education Transformations*. 2021 Aug;35. [10.16920/jeet/2022/v35is3/22133](https://doi.org/10.16920/jeet/2022/v35is3/22133).
- 14) Tariq MB, Habib HA. A Reinforcement Learning Based Recommendation System to Improve Performance of Students in Outcome Based Education Models. *IEEE Access*. 2024 Feb;12. [10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3370852](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3370852).
- 15) Ndukwe IG, Daniel BK, Butson RJ. Data Science Approach for Simulating Educational Data: Towards the Development of Teaching Outcome Model (TOM). *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*. 2018 Aug;2. [10.3390/bdcc2030024](https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc2030024).
- 16) Kaspi S, Venkatraman S. Data-Driven Decision-Making (DDDM) for Higher Education Assessments: A Case Study. *Systems*. 2023 Jun;11:306. [10.3390/systems11060306](https://doi.org/10.3390/systems11060306).
- 17) Othman N, Saat EHM, Muhamad NA, Anuar NHK, Majid MA. The Development of an Outcome-Based Education (OBE) System for Measuring Student Programme Attainment. *Journal of Computing Research and Innovation*. 2024 Sep;9(2). [10.24191/jcrinn.v9i2.472](https://doi.org/10.24191/jcrinn.v9i2.472).
- 18) Aminah S, Krisnadhii AA, Hidayanto AN. Ontological Framework for the Analysis of Outcome-Based Curriculum in Higher Education. *IEEE Access*. 2025 Feb;13. [10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3542881](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3542881).
- 19) Paulsen L, Lindsay E. Learning analytics dashboards are increasingly becoming about learning and not just analytics - A systematic review. *Education and Information Technologies*. 2024 Jan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12401-4>.